

A New Combination and a Name at New Rank in *Epiphyllum* (Cactaceae)

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Abstract—The new combination *Epiphyllum* ×*bauericardium* and the name at new rank *Epiphyllum phyllanthus* subsp. *plattsii* are proposed.

The name ×*Seleniphyllum bauericardium* was published in 2016 for a hybrid between *Epiphyllum baueri* and *Selenicereus chrysocardium*. Since the latter species is now also included in *Epiphyllum*, a new combination is necessary. Urs Eggli (in [Repert. Pl. Succ. LXVII \(2016\): 15. 2018](#)) considered the epithet invalid under the articles H.10.1 and H.10.2 of the Melbourne Code ([McNeill & al. in Regnum Veg. 154. 2012](#)), which are practically identical to those in the Shenzhen Code ([Turland & al. in Regnum Veg. 159. 2018](#)), but it is in fact acceptable, although discouraged in Recommendation H.10A of both Codes.

Epiphyllum* ×*bauericardium (E.Meier & Mangelsdorff) M.van der Meer **comb. nov.**

≡ ×*Seleniphyllum bauericardium* E.Meier & Mangelsdorff – EPIG 76: 11 (2016)

= *Epiphyllum baueri* Dorsch × *Epiphyllum chrysocardium* Alexander (≡ *Selenicereus chrysocardium* (Alexander) Kimnach)

<https://www.cactusnames.org/epiphyllum-bauericardium>

The name *Epiphyllum phyllanthus* var. *plattsii* was published in 2012 for a taxon endemic to the Cayman Islands. Following the recommendation by the IOS Working Party to use the rank of subspecies instead of that of variety (Hunt, New Cactus Lexicon: 4. 2006), a name at new rank is proposed here:

***Epiphyllum phyllanthus* subsp. *plattsii* (Proctor) M.van der Meer stat. nov.**

≡ *Epiphyllum phyllanthus* var. *plattsii* Proctor — Fl. Cayman Islands 256 (2012)

<https://www.cactusnames.org/epiphyllum-phyllanthus-subsp-plattsii>

